

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Overview of Microspheres: An Advanced Drug Delivery System

Bhushan Shewale*, Shraddha Bhavsar, Dr. Gokul Talele, Jayashree Bhamre

Research student, Department of Pharmaceutics, Matoshri College of Pharmacy, (MH), India

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27 July 2024

Accepted: 30 July 2024

Published: 31 July 2024

Keywords:

microsphere, applications, evaluation, and types of microspheres

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13142952

ABSTRACT

Microspheres are small particles with a sphere-like shape that range in size from 1 to 1000 micrometres . These are spherical, freely-moving particles that can be produced using artificial polymers or proteins. A controlled, extended release of a therapeutic substance can be achieved by a variety of techniques. which logically breaks down. Two distinct forms of microspheres are microcapsules and micromatrices. There are several different types of microspheres described. One of the most widely used types, microspheres have several advantages. These pre-made microspheres can be filled with a solid gelatin or compressed. Microspheres can be made using a variety of techniques, including as spray drying, solvent evaporation, phase separation coacervation, single-emulsion, and double-emulsion. A range of assessment techniques are used to evaluate microspheres, and they are also investigated.

INTRODUCTION

Microspheres are defined as solid, generally spherical objects that have a diameter between one and a thousand micrometres. They can have the shape of microcrystalline crystals or medications that have been distributed in certain solutions. It's common to use the terms "microspheres" and "microcapsules" interchangeably. Microspheres are sometimes referred to as microparticles. Various materials, both natural and synthetic, can be used to create microspheres. Glass, polymer, and ceramic microspheres are among the materials that are commercially accessible. The microsphere plays a critical role. Enhance the assimilation of

conventional medications and reduce adverse reactions. The microspheres are particles, spherical and freely circulating, composed of naturally occurring biodegradable polymers. There are two different kinds of microspheres: micromatrices and microcapsules. Microcapsules are tiny containers with a distinct capsule wall enclosing the contents within, while micromatrices are structures in which the substance that is imprisoned is dispersed throughout the matrix. The drug particles can be distributed in a framework made up of one or more molecules at the molecular or macroscale. Miscible polymers are known as microspheres, and they are defined

***Corresponding Author:** Bhushan Shewale

Address: Research student, Department of Pharmaceutics, Matoshri College of Pharmacy, (MH), India

Email ✉: bhushan142001@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

as "monolithic spheres or therapeutic substances dispersed either throughout the matrix or as a molecular particle dispersion." The most widely used polymer microsphere types are composed of polystyrene and polyethylene. Polystyrene microspheres are a popular option for biomedical applications due to their ability to streamline procedures such as antibody precipitation and cell sorting. Because proteins and ligands link to polystyrene microspheres quickly and firmly, they are useful for scientific studies in biology and medical research. Microencapsulation is a

modifiable and delayed drug release method. Its small particle size allows it to be widely distributed throughout the digestive tract, enhancing drug absorption and minimising adverse effects. medication production in a particular location that irritates the mucosa of the gastrointestinal tract. [1-5]

Materials needed to create the microsphere: [6-10]

A polymer classified into the following categories was employed in the creation of the microsphere:

Advantages: [11-16]

1. It improves patient compliance by reducing the frequency of dosages.
2. They were spherical in shape and large enough to be injected into the body.
3. The effects of microspheres are long-lasting and continuous
4. When a drug's size is decreased, its surface area increases, perhaps improving its poor solubility.
5. The design of the microspheres enables controlled variations in the release and degradation of medicine.
6. Reduced size can improve the efficiency of a substance that is difficult to dissolve by increasing its surface area.

7. When a medication is coated with polymers to stop enzymatic cleavage, its dispersion is at its maximum.
8. Reduce your sensitivity to the external world in comparison to your core
9. Use of pharmaceuticals effectively can reduce the probability or intensity of adverse side effects and boost bioavailability.

Disadvantages: [17-21]

1. differences in the discharge rate between dosages.
2. decreased consistency
3. The regulated dose mechanism of release has a different release rate depending on a number of factors, including transfer levels through the stomach and nutrition.

4. It is not necessary to chew these dosage forms.
5. Environmentally harmful byproducts of polymer matrix degradation can be created by sunlight, heat, hydrolysis, oxidation, or biological processes.
6. There are times when preparation causes the medication content to vary.
7. The environmental impact of the polymer matrix and its efficacy.

Types of microspheres

Sr.No.	Types	Discription	Application	References
1.	Radioactive microspheres	Using radioactive microspheres, large doses of radiation can be directed to a particular location without affecting the normal tissue nearby.	liver and spleen diagnostics	22
2.	Magnetic microspheres	Using this type of delivery mechanism is crucial to getting the treatment to the actual cause of the illness.	chemotherapy drug for the liver	23-24
3	Polymeric microspheres	The various forms of polymeric microspheres can be divided into two categories: synthetic microspheres and biodegradable polymeric microspheres	Hepatitis vaccination	25
4	Bioadhesive microspheres	These microspheres were in touch with the application site for an extended period of time.	Nasal-Gentamycin	26
5	Floating microspheres	One benefit of using gastro-retentive floating carriers for drug delivery is that their bulk is less dense than that of stomach fluid.	Antibiotics for NSAIDS	27-30

Methods of Preparation

Phase separation coacervation method

The purpose of this process is to lessen the solubility of the polymer in the early phases of the natural phase, hence influencing the formation of a polymer-rich phase known as the coacervates. Using this technique, an incompatible polymer is mixed with the drug-containing polymer solution. The first polymer absorbs the drug particles, causing phase separation. A polymer solidifies due to non-solvent addition. The

process used to generate the polylactic acid (PLA) microspheres. It's a polymer that doesn't work with butadiene. The dispersion of the polymer film, particle size, and agglomeration of the generated particles are all influenced by the rate of coacervate synthesis. The process factors are crucial as a result. Agglomeration must be avoided by agitating aggressively while suspended with a stirrer running at the right speed.^[31]

Single Emulsion Method

Microparticulate carriers of naturally occurring polymers can be found in proteins and dietary sources, respectively. method of preparation with just one emulsion. The natural polymers are first dispersed or dissolved in an aqueous solution. Subsequently, the combination is put into a non-aqueous, oil-based medium. The next step of preparation involves cross-linking the fragmented globule. Materials can be crossed over using two different techniques: heat or chemicals. linking agents such formaldehyde, chloride, glutaraldehyde acid, etc.^[32-34]

Double Emulsion Method

The double emulsion method of microsphere production is a great fit for water-soluble medications, peptides, proteins, and vaccines. It entails creating several double w/o/w emulsions or emulsions. This technique can be applied to polymers that are synthetic or natural. The aqueous protein solution is dispersed throughout the lipophilic organic continuous phase. It is possible that the active ingredients are in this protein solution. The protein contained in the continuous phase is eventually wrapped by the polymer solution, which is often composed of the scattered aqueous phase. After that, the aqueous polyvinyl alcohol solution (PVA) is mixed with the primary emulsion and homogenised, or sonicated. This leads to the formation of a double emulsion. Next, the solvent needs to be removed from the emulsion, either by employing solvent.^[31]

Spray Dring Method

It is a closed, one-step system approach that works well with a wide range of materials, including heat-sensitive ones. Both the drug and the components of the polymer coating are suspended. In an emulsion or coacervate system, it can also be suspended or dissolved. The drug and polymer are dissolved using methylene chloride. For example, polylactide microspheres can be formed in the polymer solution or dissolved in an appropriate solvent (aqueous or non-aqueous). The drug

solution's delivery rate of polymers, the nozzle's size, the temperature in the drying and gathering chambers, and the diameters of the two chambers all have an impact on the size of the microspheres.^[35]

Solvent Evaporation Method

This process, which is used to produce microparticles, comprises extracting the organic phase by employing an organic solvent. Water is used in the procedure as an organic The organic phase is eliminated by water extraction and solvent miscible. The process reduces the duration of the microspheres. One method of the process is the direct insertion of the medication. Elimination is affected by a number of variables, including the volume of the emulsion in relation to the solubility profile of a polymer in water, the amount of solvent, the temperature of the water, and others.^[36-38]

Evaluation of microspheres

Percentage yield of microspheres

After being fully dried, microspheres were collected and weighed exactly. The percentage yield below was then calculated using the provided formula.

Mass of microsphere / total weight of drug divided by 100 equals yield percentage.^[39]

1. Optical microscopy

To measure particle size, an optical microscope and this approach were employed. (Optik Meizer). For the measurement, 100 particles were determined under 450x (45x objective and 10x eyepiece)^[40]

2. Thermal analysis

Thermal analysis methods regularly examine these variations by using scheduled changes in specimen pressure and atmosphere as well as changes in temperature for cooling and heating. Tiny variations in gas evolution, thermal expansion or shrinkage, weight loss or

gain, Young's modulus, and heat and enthalpy are a few of the most commonly observed characteristics.^[41]

3. Flow Property

The flow qualities can be analysed using the Carr's compressibility index, the Hausner ratio, and the resting angle of repose. Utilising a volumetric cylinder, Determine the bulk and tapped material densities.^[39]

4. Scanning Electron microscopy

To assess the surface morphology, SEM was utilised. The microcapsules were applied immediately on a sample of the SEMsluband, with the use of double-sided tape. coated with goldfilm and running at a lower pressure.^[42]

5. Entrapment Efficiency

Five milligrammes of the drug were contained in crushed microspheres, which were mixed with distilled water using an ultrasonic mixer for three hours, filtered, and then analysed using UV-vis spectroscopy. The ratio of the drug's actual to theoretical content establishes the trapping effectiveness.^[42]

6. Swelling Index

The following formula was used to calculate the microsphere's swelling index.
$$\frac{\text{Mass of swollen microspheres} - \text{mass of dry microspheres}}{\text{mass of dried microspheres}} \times 100$$
 is the swelling index.^[46-49]

8. Drug Content

The mixture must be let aside to allow the dust to settle before washing it away. One millilitre of the filtrate was added to a volumetric flask, and the volume was then modified using 0.1 N NaOH. The medication was assessed using

spectrophotometry following the appropriate dilution.^[50]

Applications of microspheres

1. Microsphere in chemotherapy

Microspheres have the greatest potential for usage as drug delivery systems for anti-tumor drugs. When microspheres were injected into the leaking vasculature, the amount of endocytic processes. Covering stealth microspheres with soluble polyoxy ethylene is a step in the procedure. The RETiculo Endothelial System (RES) non-stealth microsphere accumulation may be advantageous for cancer treatment.^[43-45]

2. Microsphere in vaccine delivery

Immunity to microbes and their harmful components is a requirement for vaccinations. The same requirement for cost-effectiveness, efficacy, and protection in An ideal vaccination should meet both application and cost. It is challenging to defend oneself and avoid unfavourable outcomes. Antibody response production volume and safety factor are intimately linked to application mode. To solve the drawbacks of conventional immunisations, the same biodegradable intravenous vaccine delivery method may be employed.^[51]

3. Gene delivery

Microspheres' GI tract adhesion and transport properties make them a potential oral gene carrier. As an example, gene therapy using the use of polycations, viral vectors, cationic liposomes, gelatine DNA plasmid complexes, chitosan, and insulin. It is also useful in the administration of vaccines because immunity to the virus or bacteria is a prerequisite for receiving one. Its product makes it unsafe. The shortcomings of traditional immunisations may be offset by biodegradable intravenous vaccine delivery systems. Diphtheria and tetanus vaccinations, among others, have been

encapsulated in biodegradable polymer microspheres for parenteral administration.^[52]

4. Oral delivery

Polymer-containing microspheres have the ability to form films, which makes them useful for creating film forms as an alternative to pill forms for pharmaceuticals. Because of their sensitivity to pH and the reactivity of primary amines, microspheres are more appropriate for use in oral drug delivery applications like gelatin and chitosan.^[52]

5. Ophthalmic drug delivery

Microspheres composed of polymers are advantageous due to their beneficial biological features, which include bioadhesion, permeation-enhancing qualities, and fascinating physicochemical properties. excellent ingredients for the production of alginate, chitosan, and gelatin as ophthalmic drug delivery agents.^[53-60]

6. Buccal Drug delivery

Two examples of polymers that work well for buccal delivery are chitosan and sodium alginate because they have mucosal/bioadhesive properties and can enhance the process of absorption.^[53-60]

7. Nasal drug delivery

It has been demonstrated that polymer-based drug delivery systems with efficient microspheres include liposomes, gels, and microspheres. As soon as they encounter the nasal mucosa, their capacity to adhere to surfaces and proliferate swiftly is enhanced. the duration of a medication's nasal delivery system and its bioavailability. For example, albumin, dextran, starch, gelatin, and chitosan.^[61]

CONCLUSION

Microspheres have been discovered to be a better option for medication delivery when compared to several other forms of drug delivery systems. Different kinds of procedures for preparation are being studied. It contains microspheres used in

gene delivery, nasal delivery, oral delivery, and other microsphere applications. Microspheres will play a major role in medicine in the future.

REFERENCE

1. Chithambara Thanoo B, Sunny MC, Jayakrishnan A. Cross-linked chitosan microspheres: preparation and evaluation as a matrix for the controlled release of pharmaceuticals. *Journal of pharmacy and pharmacology*. 1992;44(4):283-6.
2. Reddy BV, Krishnaveni K. Formulation and evaluation of efavirenz microspheres. *Der Pharmacia letters*. 2015;7(6):1-9.
3. Virmani T, Gupta J. Pharmaceutical application of microspheres: an approach for the treatment of various diseases. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2017;8(8):3253-60.
4. Li SP, Kowarski CR, Feld KM, Grim WM. Recent advances in microencapsulation technology and equipment. *Drug Development and Industrial Pharmacy*. 1988 Jan 1;14(2-3):353-76.
5. Sahil K, Akanksha M, Premjeet S, Bilandi A, Kapoor B. Microsphere: A review. *Int. J. Res. Pharm. Chem*. 2011;1(4):1184-98.
6. Margel S, Wiesel E. Acrolein polymerization: monodisperse, homo, and hybrid microspheres, synthesis, mechanism, and reactions. *Journal of Polymer Science: Polymer Chemistry Edition*. 1984 Jan;22(1):145-58.
7. Wakiyama N, Juni K, Nakano M. Preparation and evaluation in vitro of polylactic acid microspheres containing local anesthetics. *Chemical and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 1981 Nov 25;29(11):3363-8.
8. Kreuter J, Nefzger M, Liehl E, CzokR VR. Microspheres—A Novel Approach in Drug Delivery System. *J Pharm sci*. 1983;72:1146 .
9. Patel NR, Patel DA, Bharadia PD, Pandya V, Modi D. Microsphere as a novel drug

- delivery. *International Journal of Pharmacy & Life Sciences*. 2011 Aug 1;2(8).
10. Toshio Y, Mitsuru H, Shozo M, Hitoshi S. Specific delivery of mitomycin c to the liver, spleen and lung: Nano-and microspherical carriers of gelatin. *International Journal of Pharmaceutics*. 1981 Apr 1;8(2):131-41.
 11. Rathore B, Yadav A, Nayak G, Saraogi GK, Singhai AK. A review on microspheres as drug delivery carriers for management of diabetes mellitus. *International journal of pharmacy & life sciences*. 2012 Oct 1;3(10).
 12. Gullotti E, Yeo Y. Extracellularly activated nanocarriers: a new paradigm of tumor targeted drug delivery. *Molecular pharmaceutics*. 2009 Aug 3;6(4):1041-51.
 13. Alagusundaram M, Chetty MS, Umashankari K, Badarinath AV, Lavanya C, Ramkanth S. Microspheres as a novel drug delivery system: A review. *Int J Chem Tech Res*. 2009 Jul;1(3):526-34.
 14. Herfarth H, Obermeier F, Andus T, Rogler G, Nikolaus S, Kuehbacher T, Schreiber S. Improvement of arthritis and arthralgia after treatment with infliximab (Remicade) in a German prospective, open-label, multicenter trial in refractory Crohn's disease. *Official journal of the American College of Gastroenterology| ACG*. 2002 Oct 1;97(10):2688-90.
 15. Virmani T, Gupta J. Pharmaceutical application of microspheres: an approach for the treatment of various diseases. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2017;8(8):3253-60.
 16. Kavita K, Ashvini VR, Ganesh NS. Albumin microspheres. Unique system as drug delivery carriers for non steroidal anti inflammatory drugs. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*. 2010;5(2):10.
 17. Asija R, Sharma D, Mali KR. Solvent evaporation matrix erosion method: a novel approach for floating microsphere development. *J Drug Discovery and Therapeutics*. 2014;2(21):24-9.
 18. Prasad BS, Gupta VR, Devanna N, Jayasurya K. Microspheres as drug delivery system-a review. *J Glob Trends Pharm Sci*. 2014;5(3):1961-72.
 19. Lachman L, Lieberman HA, Kanig JL. *The theory and practice of industrial pharmacy*. Philadelphia: Lea & Febiger; 1976.
 20. Yuen MF, Lai CL. Treatment of chronic hepatitis B: Evolution over two decades. *Journal of gastroenterology and hepatology*. 2011 Jan;26:138-43.
 21. Prasad BS, Gupta VR, Devanna N, Jayasurya K. Microspheres as drug delivery system-a review. *J Glob Trends Pharm Sci*. 2014;5(3):1961-72.
 22. Cleland JL, Duenas ET, Park A, Daugherty A, Kahn J, Kowalski J, Cuthbertson A. Development of poly-(D, L-lactide-coglycolide) microsphere formulations containing recombinant human vascular endothelial growth factor to promote local angiogenesis. *Journal of Controlled Release*. 2001 May 14;72(1-3):13-24.
 23. Rizzetto M, Tassopoulos NC, Goldin RD, Esteban R, Santantonio T, Heathcote EJ, Lagget M, Taak NK, Woessner MA, Gardner SD. Extended lamivudine treatment in patients with HBeAg-negative chronic hepatitis B. *Journal of hepatology*. 2005 Feb 1; 42(2):173-9.
 24. Hadziyannis SJ, Tassopoulos NC, Heathcote EJ, Chang TT, Kitis G, Rizzetto M, Marcellin P, Lim SG, Goodman Z, Wulfsohn MS, Xiong S. Adefovir dipivoxil for the treatment of hepatitis B e antigen-negative chronic hepatitis B. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2003 Feb 27;348(9):800-7.
 25. Rastogi V, Shukla SS, Singh R, Lal N, Yadav P. Microspheres: a promising drug carrier.

- Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics. 2016 May 15;6(3):18-26.
26. Thanou M, Nihot MT, Jansen M, Verhoef JC, Junginger HE. Mono-N-carboxymethyl chitosan (MCC), a polyampholytic chitosan derivative, enhances the intestinal absorption of low molecular weight heparin across intestinal epithelia in vitro and in vivo. *Journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2001 Jan 1;90(1):38-46.
 27. Kawatra M, Jain U, Ramana J. Recent advances in floating microspheres as gastro-retentive drug delivery system: A review. *Int J Recent Adv Pharm Res*. 2012;2(3):5-23.
 28. Patra CN, Dutta P, Sruti J, Rao MB. Floating microspheres: recent trends in the development of gastroretentive floating drug delivery system. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Nanotechnology (IJPSN)*. 2011 May 31;4(1):1296-306.
 29. Mukund JY, Kantilal BR, Sudhakar RN. Floating microspheres: a review. *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2012;48:17-30.
 30. Gupta R, Pathak K. Optimization studies on floating multiparticulate gastroretentive drug delivery system of famotidine. *Drug development and industrial pharmacy*. 2008 Jan 1;34(11):1201-8.
 31. Dhadde GS, Mali HS, Raut ID, Nitalikar MM, Bhutkar MA. A review on microspheres: types, method of preparation, characterization and application. *Asian Journal of Pharmacy and Technology*. 2021;11(2):149-55.
 32. Patel NR, Patel DA, Bharadia PD, Pandya V, Modi D. Microsphere as a novel drug delivery. *International Journal of Pharmacy & Life Sciences*. 2011 Aug 1;2(8).
 33. Singh C, Purohit S, Singh M, Pandey BL. Design and evaluation of microspheres: A Review. *Journal of drug delivery research*. 2013;2(2):18-27.
 34. Singh C, Purohit S, Singh M, Pandey BL. Design and evaluation of microspheres: A Review. *Journal of drug delivery research*. 2013;2(2):18-27.
 35. Kumar AM, Rao KP. Poly (palmitoyl-L-hydroxyproline ester) microspheres as potential oral controlled drug delivery system. *International journal of pharmaceutics*. 1997 Apr 14;149(1):107-14.
 36. Virmani T, Gupta J. Pharmaceutical application of microspheres: an approach for the treatment of various diseases. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2017;8(8):3253-60.
 37. Mohan ME, Sujitha HA, Rao VU, Ashok M, Kumar AB. A brief review on mucoadhesive microspheres. *IJRRPAS*. 2014;4(1):975-86.
 38. Prasanth VV, Moy AC, Mathew ST, Mathapan R. Microspheres-an overview. *International journal of research in pharmaceutical and biomedical sciences*. 2011 Apr; 2(2):332-8.
 39. Galande P, Yadav V, Borkar S. A Review on Microspheres: Preparation, Characterization and Applications. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*. 2022 Dec 14;10(6):128-33.
 40. Shaji J, Poddar A, Iyer S. Brain-targeted nasal clonazepam microspheres. *Indian Journal of pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2009 Nov;71(6):715.
 41. Gupta R, Shanthi C, Mahato AG. Characterization of Captopril-Ethyl Cellulose Microspheres by Thermal Analysis. *Int. J. Drug Dev. Res*. 2010 Apr;2:394-8.
 42. Chowdary KP, Babu JS. Permeability of ethylene vinyl acetate copolymer microcapsules: Effect of solvents. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2003;65(1):62-6.
 43. Kreuter J, Nefzger M, Liehl E, CzokR VR. Microspheres—A Novel Approach in Drug Delivery System. *J Pharm sci*. 1983;72:1146.

44. Costa P, Lobo JM. Modeling and comparison of dissolution profiles. *European journal of pharmaceutical sciences*. 2001 May 1;13(2):123-33.
45. Singh C, Purohit S, Singh M, Pandey BL. Design and evaluation of microspheres: A Review. *Journal of drug delivery research*. 2013;2(2):18-27.
46. Kakkar VA, Wani SU, Gautam SP, Qadrie ZL. Role of microspheres in novel drug delivery systems: preparation methods and applications. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research*. 2020 May 15;12(3):10-5.
47. Verma R, Verma S, Kumar S. Microsphere-a novel drug delivery system. *Research Chronicle in Health Sciences*. 2019 Jul 30;5(1):5-14.
48. Virmani T, Gupta J. Pharmaceutical application of microspheres: an approach for the treatment of various diseases. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2017;8(8):3253-60.
49. Thota S, Kusuma B, Rarevati M, Narendra P, Babu SM. Formulation and Evaluation of ethyl cellulose microspheres containing diclofenac sodium. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences and Technology*. 2021 Oct 25;2(4).
50. Venkatesh DP, Karki R, Jha SK, Geetha LA, Santha KG, Goli D. Formulation and evaluation of microspheres containing fluvastatin sodium. *International Journal of Drug Development and Research*. 2012;4(2):306-14.
51. Sailaja AK, Begum N. Formulation and evaluation of cox-2 inhibitor (etoricoxib) loaded ethyl cellulose nanoparticles for topical drug delivery. *Nano Biomedicine and Engineering*. 2018 Mar 31;10(1):1-9.
52. Hafeli U. Physics and Chemistry Basic of Biotechnology. *Focus on biotechnology*. Review. *Radioactive Microspheres for Medical Application*. 2002;7:213-48.
53. Goud CM, Sravan M, Vinod M, Ramana H, Venkateshwarlu G. INVITRO WASSH OFF COMPARISION STUDIES OF SODIUM ALGINATE MUCOADHESIVE MICROSPHERES USING DIFFERENT POLYMERS.
54. Kumar A, Mahajan S, Bhandari N. Microspheres: a review. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2017 Feb 14;14(6):724-40.
55. Nikam VK, Gudsoorkar VR, Hiremath SN, Dolas RT, Kashid VA. Microspheres-A Novel drug delivery system: An overview. *International journal of pharmaceutical and chemical sciences*. 2012 Jan;1(1):113-28.
56. Meghna KS, Pillai K, Giridas S, Sreelakshmi C, Vijayakumar B. Microsphere a drug delivery system—a review. *International Journal of Novel Trends in Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2017 Aug 31;7(4):109-18.
57. Mahapatra Bk, Kumar Shah S, Mohanto S, Mantry S. Preparation Design and In-Vitro Evaluation of Sustained Release Microsphere of Ropinirole Hydrochloride By Emulsion Solvent Evaporation Technique. *International Journal of Innovative Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*. 2019 May 27; 7(5):48-60
58. Rajput S, Agrawal P, Pathak A, Shrivastava N, Baghel SS, Baghel RS. A review on microspheres: Methods of preparation and evaluation. *World journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences*. 2012;1(1).
59. Jadhav N, Patel V, Mungekar S, Bhamare G, Karpe M, Kadams V. Microsponge delivery system: an updated review, current status and future prospects. *Journal of Scientific and Innovative Research*. 2013 Sep 21;2(6):1097-110.

60. Jain NK, editor. Progress in controlled and novel drug delivery systems. CBS Publishers & Distributors; 2004.
61. Khan MS, Doharey V. A review on nasal microsphere. International Journal of Pharma Sciences. 2014;4:496-506.

HOW TO CITE: Bhushan Shewale*, Shraddha Bhavsar, Dr. Gokul Talele, Jayashree Bhamre, Overview of Microspheres: An Advanced Drug Delivery System, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2024, Vol 2, Issue 7, 2300-2309. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142952>

